

MODIFICATION OF EPOXY RESIN AND ITS INFLUENCE ON TENSILE PROPERTIES OF VISCOSE FABRIC COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with the modification of the epoxy resin which is intended to be used in viscose fabric composite production. The epoxy resin has been modified with silane coupling agent at different reaction conditions. The increase in the epoxide equivalent weight (EEW) determined through (ASTM D1652-11e1) and the increase in viscosity of modified epoxy resins, indicate the reaction between the amino group in silane coupling agent and epoxide group in the resin. The viscosity of the resin obtained after the modification is within the range of infusion resins. The commonly used gelcoats are polyester based and generally it is considered that due to the similarity in chemistry the polyester matrix resin adhere very well to polyester gelcoat. However compatibility of epoxy matrix resin and polyester gelcoat is relatively low. In this study the adhesive strength of the modified resin to conventional polyester gelcoat is measured through pull off adhesion testing (ISO 4624:2002) and contact angle measurement. Since the modified resin is intended to be used in composite production, it is also important to know the mechanical properties of the cured resin. Tensile testing of the cured modified resins was also measured in order to monitor the change in properties of modified resins with respect to cured unmodified resin. The modified epoxy/viscose fabric composites are prepared through vacuum infusion technique and the tensile properties of composites are studied with respect to unmodified resin/ viscose fabric composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins are major engineering polymers with high thermal stability, high tensile strength and modulus, low shrinkage, good adhesion strength, good electrical insulation properties and good resistance to chemical corrosion, compared to unsaturated polyester and vinyl ester resin [1]. Thus epoxy resin find its applications as; adhesives, surface coatings and painting materials, moulding compounds, microelectronic materials, printed circuit boards and as matrix material in fibre reinforced composites [2] [3]. Mechanical properties of fibre reinforced composites depends on the compatibility between the polymer matrix and the reinforcement. A good bonding between the matrix and reinforcement is essential to achieve effective stress transfer between matrix and the fibre, which in turn reduces the stress concentrations and improves overall mechanical properties [4]. Natural fibres are used as reinforcement in polymer composites, but their inherent hydrophilic nature reduces its compatibility with the hydrophobic polymer matrices. The regenerated cellulose fibres as e.g. viscose rayon, possess high purity, uniformity and reproducibility of their properties compared to lignocellulose fibres [5]. Thus regenerated cellulose fibre can be an alternative or a parallel choice for lignocellulose fibres in polymer composites. The two main approaches to improve the fibre-matrix interaction are the surface modification of fibre [6] [7] [8] and the matrix modification [4] [9]. Through the matrix modification, reactive sites are introduced in the matrix resin with higher chemical affinity towards the reactive groups present in the fibre.

The modification of epoxy resin to improve the toughness through reactive liquid rubber [10], improving the corrosion resistance and adhesion of epoxy coatings on aluminium surface using silane coupling agents [11], and improving the water resistance between epoxy coatings and metal substrate

through silanes are reported in literature [12]. Epoxy resin was modified with Poly (styrene-co-acrylonitrile) (SAN) to improve the toughness and the mechanical properties of glass fibre composite prepared with SAN modified epoxy resin were studied [13]. The mechanical properties of silane modified epoxy resin/glass fibre composite was studied and was seen that the composites were exhibiting improved mechanical properties [14]. The epoxy resin were modified with different silane coupling agents and the mechanical properties of its composite with carbon fibre was also studied [15]. However the studies related to natural fibre composites prepared from modified thermoset resin are few reported [16]. Specifically the modification of epoxy resin using silane coupling agent and studying its influence on the mechanical properties of regenerated cellulose fibre composites are rarely found in literature

Silane coupling agents have a general chemical structure of $R_{(4-n)}-Si-(R'X)_n$ ($n=1, 2$), where R is alkoxy, X is any organofunctionality and R' is the alkyl bridge connecting the silicone atom and organofunctionality. This bifunctionality of organosilanes facilitates an effective coupling between cellulosic fibres and polymer matrices [17]. Silane coupling agent which is commonly used to modify the fibre surface can also be used to modify the thermoset resins. The alkoxy groups in the silane coupling agent are capable to react with the fibre surface, while the organic functionalities such as amino, mecapto, glycidoxo, vinyl or methacryloxy groups present in silane, form chemical bond with reactive sites present in the matrix resin. Thus it will result in good fibre-matrix interaction, through which the mechanical properties of composites are improved. The main objective of this study is to modify the commercial epoxy resin with silane coupling agent and assess the effect of modification on the tensile properties of the viscose fabric reinforced composites. The adhesion of the modified epoxy resin to polyester based gelcoat is also measured in this study.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

The epoxy resin, (Prime 20LV) and curing agent (Prime 20LV slow hardener) manufactured by Gurit Ltd were used. The silane coupling agent used for resin modification was 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES; 99% purity) and was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All the chemicals used in titration were of reagent grade and were used without further purification. The polyester gelcoat used in this study is Endguard GE (white) from Ashland Inc, Finland, which is suitable for brush application. Methyl ethyl ketone peroxide was used as curing agent for polyester gelcoat. The fabric used as the reinforcement in the preparation of composites for pull off adhesion test and tensile tests were based on viscose yarn with the twist Z40, 2440 dtex linear density and 1350 filaments (Cordenka CR). The yarn was processed by warp knitting into unidirectional fabrics with a surface weight of 223 g/m² (Engtex, Sweden).

2.2. Modification of epoxy resin

About 100g of epoxy resin was taken in a 250ml round bottom flask equipped with a reflux condenser. Different amount of silane coupling agent was added in to the flask to achieve 1%, 3% and 5% APTES by mass of epoxy resin. The mixture was stirred using a magnetic stirrer at 70°C for 1 hour. The resin modified with 1%, 3% and 5% APTES by mass of epoxy resin is designated as 1APTES, 3APTES, and 5APTES, respectively.

2.3. Preparation of composites

The composite for the pull-off adhesion test was prepared through hand layup method. The gelcoat was applied on the glass plate which was previously waxed and polished. Application of gelcoat was done using a paint brush to achieve a thickness of ≈ 0.5 mm. The gelcoat was left at room temperature for 18 hours for curing. Soon after the curing time, four layers of unidirectional viscose fabric was laid ($\pm 0/\pm 90/\pm 0/\pm 90$) on the gelcoat surface. This was followed by wetting with epoxy resin with 26% by weight of hardener. After the proper wetting of the fabric, the glass plate was kept in an oven at 65°C

for 7 hours and 80°C for 2 hours. The time interval between the end of initial curing and start of post curing was 18 hours.

The composite sheet for the tensile testing were prepared through vacuum infusion. The mould preparation and general infusion process was done according to a previous study [17]. The differences in the procedure is that, in this study the infusion resin used was epoxy and lower vacuum of ≈ -0.1 bar was applied during the process. The temperature during infusion process was 65°C for 7 hours and the vacuum was applied until 1 hour after infusion, by the time which resin got cured. The post curing was done at 80°C for 2 hours. The composites produced from 1APTES, 3APTES, and 5APTES modified epoxy resins are designated as C 1APTES, C 3APTES, and C 5APTES respectively.

3. CHARACTERIZATION

3.1. Epoxy content of epoxy resin

The epoxy content of epoxy resin was determined according to ASTM D1652-11 [18]. The resin was dissolved in methylene chloride and the titration was done with standard perchloric acid in the presence of an excess of tetraethylammonium bromide. Hydrogen bromide generated in situ by the addition of perchloric acid to the quaternary ammonium halide, rapidly opens the epoxide ring. Therefore, the quantity of acid consumed is a measure of the epoxy content. More details on the test method is described in the ASTM D1652-11.

3.2. Viscosity measurement

The viscosity of the unmodified and APTES modified epoxy resins were measured using Anton Paar MCR 301 rheometer and the conditions used were; shear rate: 10 1/s, and temperature range: 25°C – 65°C. The test was done with a 25 mm plate-plate measuring system at a gap of 1mm. The values reported are average of the two parallel measurements.

3.3. Tensile properties of cured resins

The tensile testing of cured, unmodified and modified resins were conducted according to ISO 527-1 using Tiratest 2705 tensile testing machine equipped with a 5kN load cell. The data was analyzed with TIRAtest system software. Tensile test specimens were cured at 65°C for 7 h, in the mould with dimensions specified for dog-bone shaped tensile specimen in ISO 527-1. Dimensions of the testing area were 80mm of length of narrow portion, 10mm of average width of narrow portion and 4mm of an average thickness. Overall, length of the specimens was 150mm. The test was carried out at ambient temperature with a testing speed of 2mm/min. The tensile strength and elongation at break are calculated as average of five specimens.

3.4. Contact angle measurements on cured resins

Contact angles were measured from the surfaces of the cured modified and unmodified epoxy resins to compare the surface nature of the resin after curing reaction. Contact angles were measured by imaging the droplet on the surface of the composites using Advex Instruments system. The volume of drop was 3 μ l. The test liquids used to measure the contact angle was ultra pure water and diiodomethane. The measurements were repeated on 5 different spots on the surface and the average value is reported.

3.4. Pull-off adhesion testing

Pull-off adhesion testing was done on epoxy/viscose-fabric test panels with an average size of 11cm x 11cm, prepared through hand layup method. The test was done at a tensile stress increasing at a rate not greater than 1MPa/s. The test was conducted using a sand blasted 20mm steel dolly. The gelcoat surface was highly glossy which made it necessary to be sanded. After gentle sanding, the dolly was

attached to the gelcoat surface using an epoxy adhesive, (Araldite Rapid). The excess resin was cleaned of the test area and the dolly was taped to prevent any unwanted movement during curing. The curing of adhesive was done according to the datasheet from the manufacturer; 16hours at 40°C. The test area was separated from other part by using a hole saw.

3.5. Tensile properties of epoxy/viscose fabric composite

The tensile testing of epoxy/viscose fabric composite were conducted according to ISO 527-1 on a Tiratest 2705 tensile testing machine equipped with a 5kN load cell. The data was analyzed with TIRAtest system software. Tensile test specimens were machined into dog-bone shape through mechanical cutting. Dimensions of the testing area were 80mm of length of narrow portion, 10mm of average width of narrow portion and 2mm of an average thickness. Overall, length of the specimens was 150mm. The test specimens were conditioned in a climatic chamber for 16 hours at 23°C temperature and 50% relative humidity. The test was carried out at ambient temperature with a testing speed of 2mm/min. The tensile strength and elongation at break are calculated as average of five specimens.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Testing of modified epoxy resins

The titration method to determine epoxide group content of resins was utilised in order to verify the reaction of APTES silane and epoxy resin. The results obtained from the titration method according to ASTM D1652-11 are listed in the Table1. It is seen from the results in Table 1 that the weight percent epoxide is decreasing with the increasing content of APTES in modification. Correspondingly the value for epoxide equivalent weight is increased to 211 g/mol for 5APTES from 184 g/mol for unmodified. The epoxide equivalent weight EEW, is the weight in grams of resin containing 1 mole equivalent of epoxide (g/mol). These results indicate that the modification of epoxy resin with the amino functional APTES silane resulted in reaction between amino group in silane and epoxide group in the epoxy resin. This indicates the coupling of amino functional silane onto the epoxy resin.

Modification	Weight percent epoxide (%)	EEW (g/mol)
Unmodified	23.4	184
1APTES	22.8	189
3APTES	21.3	202
5APTES	20.4	211

Table 1: Percent epoxide and epoxy equivalent weight of unmodified and modified resins

The viscosity measurements were done at a shear rate of 10 1/s, in a temperature range of 25°C – 65°C. The viscosity of unmodified and all the three modified resins showed a decrease in viscosity by increase in temperature. The viscosity of unmodified and modified epoxy resins at room temperature and manufacturer recommended processing temperature are tabulated in Table 2. The viscosity of modified resin with respect to unmodified resin, increased at both temperatures. At the room temperature, the viscosity of 5APTES increased \approx 50% if compared to unmodified. At the recommended processing temperature (65°C), the viscosity gradually increased with increase in silane content. The increase in the viscosity of modified resins can be attributed to the ring opening reaction of epoxide with amino functionality in APTES. The increase in viscosity of modified resin supplement the results inferred from the titration method, that a coupling reaction has taken place between epoxy resin and APTES.

Modification	Average viscosity (mPa.s)	
	25°C	65°C
Unmodified	614	36
1APTES	716	41
3APTES	891	48
5APTES	1185	61

Table 2: Viscosity of the APTES modified resins at room temperature and processing temperature

4.2. Contact angle measurement of cured resin

The contact angle is a direct measure of the wettability of a liquid on a surface, which is connected with the total surface energy of the measured surface. This method measures the angle between the outline tangent of a liquid drop deposited on a solid and the surface of that solid. In this study the change of wetting behavior of modified and unmodified epoxy resin surfaces was estimated and further study on the surface free energy was not performed.

Figure 1: The water contact angle (WCA) and diiodomethane contact angle (DIM) on the unmodified and APTES modified cured epoxy resin

The Figure 1 illustrates the water and diiodomethane contact angles on unmodified and modified cured resin surface. Both the water and diiodomethane contact angles showed an increasing trend with increased amount of silane modification. The simultaneous decreasing trend of water and diiodomethane contact angle with increase in hydrophilicity for polymer surface is reported in the literature [19]. Then the water and DIM contact angles are assumed to show an increasing trend when the hydrophilicity is decreasing. The WCA increased from 85° for unmodified resin to 99° for 5APTES showing that the APTES modification has made the cured polymer surface hydrophobic compared to cured unmodified resin. When a thermoset resin is considered to be fully cured, less amount of reactive sites are available on the surface of cured resin. One reason for the cured epoxy resins absorbing water is the presence of hydroxyl groups, which is formed during the ring opening of epoxide during the cross linking reaction. In the case of APTES modified resins, it is assumed that the hydroxyl groups formed during the curing of resin reacts with the reactive sites in the silane which is attached to it. According to this, the hydrophilic nature of cured epoxy resin is decreased by the functionalization of the polar OH groups with hydrophobic silyl moieties [20]. It is then anticipated that the moisture resistance of composites made from APTES modified epoxy resin will be better compared to composite made from unmodified resin.

4.3. Pull-off adhesion testing of polyester gelcoat

The pull-off test was carried out to determine the adhesion strength of polyester gelcoat applied on the epoxy resin. According to literature the breaking strength in a range of 2–4 MPa corresponds to acceptable paint adhesion and anything above 4 MPa is classified as good and 20 MPa is the upper limit for the test in general [21] [22]. According to reference [22], method described in ISO 4624 is the best suited to measure gelcoat adhesion. It is considered that if the coating system has very good adhesion, either cohesive failure of coating or substrate can occur [21]. The breaking strength obtained from the pull off test is listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Breaking strength of gelcoat with respect to modification of resin

It was noticed from the inspection of area on each side of the site of separation that the prominent nature of failure was adhesive failure between adhesive and dolly, in all the tested specimens. Another notable nature of failure occurred was cohesive failure of substrate. The failure between substrate and gelcoat which indicates low adhesion of epoxy to gelcoat was not found in any of the tested specimen. The results shows that the adhesive strength is higher than 4 MPa, which is categorized good for the painting systems. According to this it can be concluded that the adhesive strength of epoxy resin on polyester gelcoat is good enough.

4.4. Tensile properties of epoxy/viscose fabric composite

The influence of the resin modification on the tensile strength of epoxy composites and cured epoxy resin is shown in Figure 2. The improvement in strength of all the composites compared to unreinforced resin is obviously due to reinforcing effect of viscose fabric. The APTES modification reduced the tensile strength of 3APTES and 5APTES modified resin with respect to unmodified resin, while the strength of 1APTES modified resin was almost similar to unmodified resin. It is evident from analyzing the Figure 2, that the tensile strength of epoxy composites increase with increasing amount of APTES modification. There was an increase of 12% for C 1APTES and 16% for C 5APTES in tensile strength with respect to C Unmodified composites. This improvement in strength of C 1APTES and C 5APTES can be attributed to the the modification of epoxy resin. Through modification, more reactive sites are available in resin, which might have reacted with hydroxyl groups present on the regenerated cellulose fibre. Hence the epoxy resin modification has improved the compatibility between the reinforcement and the resin, resulting in composite with improved tensile properties.

Figure 2: Tensile strength of cured resin and composites with respect to resin modification

The elongation at break of composites and cured resins are presented in Figure 3. It is seen that the elongation of 3APTES and 5APTES unreinforced cured resins, increased with the modification of the resin. This can be ascribed to the flexible siloxane bond (Si-O-Si) introduced to the resin by silane modification [23] [24]. This needed to be verified by FTIR analysis in future. The elongation at break value for the viscose yarn (Cordenka CR[®]) from which the fabric under study is produced is reported to be much higher than other lignocellulose fibres [25]. The reinforcing effect of viscose yarn is evident from the improvement of elongation at break of the viscose fabric reinforced epoxy resin composites. It is notable that the 1APTES modification has improved the viscose fabric composite properties significantly, without compromising the non-reinforced cured resin properties.

Figure 3: Effect of resin modification on the elongation at break of cured resins and composites

5. CONCLUSIONS

The epoxy resin was modified with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) at three different concentrations at similar conditions. The efficiency of the silane modification was confirmed through the titration test according to ASTM D1652-11 and by measuring the viscosity change after the modification of the epoxy resin. In future more analysis like FTIR will be carried out to confirm the silane modification of epoxy resin. There was no visible failure between the substrate and the gelcoat noted during the pull-off adhesion testing, and the preliminary conclusion can be made that the adhesive strength is more than 4 MPa, which is categorized as good breaking strength for painting systems. The contact angle measurement results from the surface of cured epoxy resin shows that with higher content of silane modification, the hydrophilic property of epoxy resin is reduced. So it is anticipated that the

composites made from modified epoxy resin will be better in moisture resistance compared to those made from unmodified resin. The tensile properties of the composites were improved as the content of silane coupling agent was increased. This indicates improved compatibility between the cellulose fibre and the modified epoxy resin, which is due to chemical bonding between fibre and silane modified resin. In the future the flexural properties of composites and water absorption properties of the modified epoxy/viscose fabric composites with and without gelcoat will be investigated.

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